

A Context-Aware Carbon Footprint Calculator for Sustainable Tourism in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Tourism is one of the fastest-growing industries worldwide, yet it contributes significantly to global carbon emissions. In Sri Lanka, existing carbon footprint calculators often rely on generalized international datasets that fail to account for local factors such as hybrid transport systems, accommodation types, and cultural practices. This research proposes a context-aware carbon footprint calculator tailored to Sri Lanka's tourism sector, integrating localized emission benchmarks and real-time trip monitoring. The study aims to design and implement a web-based system that enables tourists and travel agents to input travel details, calculate accurate emissions, and receive personalized sustainability recommendations. By combining Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority (SLTDA) data, traveler itineraries, and vehicle-specific inputs, the proposed solution bridges existing gaps in localization, personalization, and verification. The anticipated outcomes include: (1) a functional web-based calculator, (2) real-time tracking of carbon emissions in vehicles using IoT tools with user consent, enabling precise monitoring of actual travel-related emissions, and (3) actionable sustainability recommendations that bridge the awareness-behavior gap. This accessible tool empowers tourists to make eco-conscious decisions and support Sri Lanka's sustainable tourism goals.

Keywords: *Sustainable Tourism, Carbon Footprint, Context-Aware Systems, Emission Calculator, Sri Lanka.*